

**NATURAL
HISTORY
MUSEUM**

Conflict avoidance:

**Balancing the display needs with
the conservation requirements at
the Natural History Museum**

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Our Conflicts

Display

Research

Events

Estates

Finance

Specimen

Where?

Gallery 30 contains 78 specimens which have been mounted on the wall since the 1920's.

This is the most comprehensive and important collection of Lower Jurassic fossil marine reptiles on display in any museum. The wall also contains many specimens which are actively being researched.

The collection contains many historic, type and figured specimens and many of the localities from where they were collected no longer exist.

The project

In 2009 the Conservation Unit started a program to resolve a long-standing problem of moisture migration through a south facing wall in one of main galleries at the Natural History Museum.

The problem was first observed as a serious mould growth on the MDF surrounds to the specimens.

Following detailed inspection of 22 specimens on the gallery wall it was decided to remove 9 specimens from the wall for conservation work and until the problem could be fully resolved.

Accessing the specimens

Our initial condition survey was undertaken with a Cherry Picker.

It quickly became clear that complete inspection of the specimens was not possible and that we needed better access to them.

A decision was made to put scaffolding up across both sets of specimens that were at risk. This was so that the glass could be removed from the front of the specimens and if necessary specimens removed from the wall.

Stages of Planning

- Project review (Prince2)
- Condition Reports
- Gant chart of work required
- Full costing of project (to acquire funding from capital bids group)
 - Loss of revenue (events)
- Risk from not undertaking work
- Site Risk Documentation
 - Scaffolding
 - Temporary Conservation Labs
- Establish and set up temporary labs
- Dates for scaffolding and work in galleries identified and cleared
- Ensure staff available to undertake work
- Project work program (adapted throughout project)

Development of Plan

Once scaffolding inspection was underway, we were able to revise our project plan and produce a realistic costing for the project.

Including 3D imaging (to improve research access)

Original estimates were £140K

6 month project

Mould and insects on specimens

Mould was observed growing on the surrounds to the specimens (at the west end of the gallery). The humidity had risen in excess of 70%. As there was no air exchange within the gallery, the conditions for mould growth had arisen. An infestation of Book lice and plaster beetle was also observed on all the specimens.

Condition of Specimens

Conservation Unit staff surveyed 22 specimens on the wall.

Most required superficial interventive work, remedial cleaning (mould and dust) and surface restoration – with scaffolding in place we could work on them on the wall.

The largest of the specimens, however, required a complete remount due to instability and deterioration. The specimen is over 4m long and weighs 1.5 tons and was (of course) at the top of the wall.

Since the wall and the specimens were extremely damp, it was decided to remove the specimens from the west end of the wall where the problems were the most serious wall. They could then be treated and the wall could dry out.

The Problem?

Blocked and overflowing gutters were found to have saturated the external face of the wall. In heavy rain, the shallow gutters overflowed and water cascaded down the walls. The wall is a single 20" block through which the water had migrated into the back of the specimens and then through the specimens. Trapped behind glass at the front of the specimens, the humidity had risen to over 70% RH.

A repeat problem

The problem had occurred before!

A full survey was carried out in 1989 showing that both the specimens and the wall were effected by damp.

A conservation project involving the removal of as many specimens as possible from wall (67) was started.

In 1995 the lab completed the conservation of 58 specimens across the entire gallery wall.

External repairs were made to the wall and restoration work undertaken on the specimens. It was assumed that the problem was resolved!

Cost of this project was an estimated £200,000.

Clearly we are keen that this time the problem is fully resolved!

Environmental Conditions in Gallery and behind specimens

Environmental monitoring in the gallery indicated that the relative humidity between the glass and the specimens was consistently in excess of 70%.

The external gallery space was consistently at a lower relative humidity.

Because the specimens were tightly sealed to the rear wall, the lack of any air exchange between the back of the specimen and the wall had led to moisture build up in the specimens.

Fig 3. RH/T charts for Gallery 3 and Marine Invertebrates Gallery (vivid green line)

Protection Prior to removal

Prior to removal from the wall the specimens were all protected with Plastazote™ foam.

Because the face of the large specimen was very fragile due to the level of deterioration, it was also faced with Japanese tissue and Paraloid™ B72, and then covered with a Wacker™ silicon rubber.

Moving the Specimens

The mounted vertebrates are chunks of limestone or shale, mounted in a block of Plaster of Paris, supported in a wooden frame. As such they behave structurally in the same way as large paintings – but fail brittly.

The large specimens flex longitudinally and laterally leading to cracking at right angles to each of the wooden frames. Differential movement in parallel sides of the frame leads to shear cracking in the plaster support to the specimens.

Moving the Specimens

The museum employed the same external contractors who put the specimens into their current position to remove them from the wall.

Once protected (with Plastazote™ facing) specimens were removed from the wall and attached to a sling and hoist system. They were then lowered directly into plastic bags (into which they were sealed) and then moved to the temporary quarantine and conservation lab.

Moving the specimens

Movement of specimen onto work platform

Working on the specimens

The conservation lab was not big enough to hold and work on the specimens due to their size and the need to quarantine them during the pest treatment.

Space had to be negotiated with front of house and empty galleries were turned into temporary labs for the conservation work to take place. In the end 3 different display galleries were used as temporary labs as we moved specimens to fit in with the gallery exhibition programs. With each move, we worked alongside the move team.

Solving the Pest Problem

The specimens were treated using anoxic environments to remove the pest problem. All specimens removed from the wall were sealed into barrier film bags (Escal and Marvelseal).

These were purged with dry nitrogen until the oxygen levels dropped to below 0.3%. They were then held at this oxygen level for 30 days.

Following treatment no pests were observed.

Because the specimens were damp they were used to buffer the relative humidity inside the enclosures for the period of treatment.

Both during and after treatment, a trapping program was instigated around them to ensure that there was no insect activity.

Conservation and Processing Work

Once the pest treatment was completed, remedial work and cleaning was undertaken on the surface of 8 of the specimens. The largest specimen required remounting. A support structure was built to protect the front of the specimen using Jesmonite™. It was then turned over so that the back of the specimen could be checked and stabilized. Again the move team was brought in to rotate the specimen onto its back.

Restoration of 40140

On inspection it was found that the back of the specimen was highly unstable. It was decided to remove the entire support for the specimen and rebuild it using more stable and rigid materials. The back was also to be built to resist moisture penetration.

Structure of Mount

Tuesday, 2 March 2010

Structure of mount

Tuesday, 2 March 2010

Restoration of 40140

Following cleaning and removal of the original mount, the specimen was protected using an inert Kevlar mesh which was bonded to the specimen with Paraloid™ B72. This acted as a separator.

An Epopast™ support backing was then moulded across the back of the specimen to provide a rigid support to the specimen. Cellite™ Panel (honey-combed aluminium board) was cut and then adhered and bolted across the back of the Epopast™ support.

Turning specimen over

Restoration of 40140

The specimen was then turned over. The front of the specimen was consolidated and restored (Paraloid B72 and glass microballoons gap-fill).

A medite ecologique facia was then attached to the face of the surround. The gaps around the specimen were then filled with a reversible fill (Paraloid B72 and glass microballoons) .

Current Position

Analysis of the environmental conditions on either side of the wall have shown that the exterior temperature of the wall is very close to dew-point. This means that the wall is consistently close to saturation. High Moisture levels and further salt efflorescence on the wall indicate that the continuing problems are not just linked to blocked gutters.

Several specimens have been put back on the wall with RH and T transmitters fitted both behind them, between the wall and the back of the specimen and at the front of the specimen behind the glass. An airspace has been put behind the specimens to attempt to generate a natural air flow across the back of the specimens.

The aim of this is to try and move saturated air from the back of the specimens to try and equilibrate the space with the (drier) main gallery space.

1 TX-4968A	T	25 TX-097A	T
2 TX-4968B	RH	26 TX-097B	RH
3 TX-4967A	T	27 TX-c683A	T
4 TX-4967B	RH	28 TX-c683B	T
5 TX-5197A	T	29 TX-c683C	T
6 TX-5197B	RH	30 TX-c683D	RH
7 TX-4576A	Lux	31 TX-c685A	T
8 TX-4576B	kLux	32 TX-c685B	T
9 TX-4576C	Mw/M2	33 TX-c685C	T
10 TX-4576D	Mw/L	34 TX-c685D	RH
11 TX-4576E	T	35 TX-c682A	T
12 TX-4576F	RH	36 TX-c682B	T
		37 TX-c682C	T
		38 TX-c682D	RH
		39 TX-c684A	T
		40 TX-c684A	T
		41 TX-c684A	T
		42 TX-c684A	RH

Moving specimens back onto wall

For a trial period (to December 2010), five specimens were moved back onto the wall. A short stepped scaffold was put in place and specimens were manually lifted up the steps and into position

Conflicts

Surprisingly **not** the finance, removal, movement or installation of the specimens, BUT

- Coordination of project across museum
 - Involving; Front of House (PEG), Estates, Collections Management and external researchers
 - Events department
- Length of Project (as we learned more)
- Allocation of staff time!

Conflicts

- Resolution of the overall problem (Still on-going).
Generating Air flow across the wall
- Assessing the risk of damage on a 10 year cycle vs complete resolution of project (cost/benefit)
- Negotiation for a space large enough for conservation staff to quarantine specimens and then work on them
- Adapting techniques because of the lack of lab facilities
- Engaging our estates department to resolve the problem quickly
- Engaging non-conservation staff in the project

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